

Chemical Hazards and Poisons Report

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Editorial

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Public Health England has now been operational for over a year*. Articles in this edition demonstrate how PHE is collaborating with national and international partners to further develop the environmental public health evidence base while continuing to deliver its core business functions. This issue of the Chemical Hazards and Poisons Report focuses on our work within Europe and on the preparedness and response to international chemical incidents.

The mechanisms for identifying, reporting and responding to cross-border public health threats in Europe are explored. The article 'Le Pong' shows how a release from an industrial plant in France in 2013 had a significant impact upon many of our emergency services in England and how having agreed mechanisms for liaising with our counterparts in Europe greatly improves our ability to respond to such events. A stricken ship off the coast of England required international collaboration to assess and mitigate the potential public health risk. Another recent 'toxic' import is the oak processionary moth and public health staff from the Netherlands share their approach to dealing with the caterpillars.

Improving air quality is one of the biggest environmental public health challenges in Europe. PHE describes its work to estimate the mortality burden associated with long-term exposure to particulate air pollution. Assessing the air quality impact of a large waste fire is the subject of two articles by the Met Office and PHE.

The Control of Major Accident Hazard (COMAH) Regulations implement the requirements of the European Seveso Directives. Articles describe the role of public health in the planning, preparedness and response to incidents at COMAH-regulated sites. If a significant accident involving hazardous materials were to occur, PHE has developed

guidance tools and the Government Decontamination Service maintains a framework of contractors available to assist with recovery and restoration. This is discussed in a series of articles.

Finally, the World Health Organization states that flooding is the most common natural hazard in Europe and England experienced significant floods last winter. Lessons from previous floods in Gloucestershire and the impact on a NHS blood manufacturing centre are presented.

The next issue of the report is planned for spring 2015; please contact us if you would like to contribute to this edition. Guidelines for authors and a permission to publish form can be found on the website at www.hpa.org.uk/chemicals/reports. Please do not hesitate to contact us about any papers you may wish to submit on chapreport@phe.gov.uk, or call us on 020 7811 7141.

We are very grateful to Andrew Tristem and Matthew Pardo for their support in preparing this issue.

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The views and opinions expressed by the authors in the Chemical Hazards and Poisons Report do not necessarily reflect those of the Board of Public Health England or of the Editor and Associate Editors.

Front cover images: flooded NHS Blood and Transport manufacturing centre, GDS framework supplier removing contaminated waste, Seal Sands refineries and Happy Lady Happy Lady (reproduced by courtesy of the Environment Agency)

* On 1 April 2013 the Health Protection Agency was abolished and its functions transferred to Public Health England.

Developing tools to assist with evaluating a recovery strategy

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Following the implementation of the Civil Contingencies Act (2004), there has been a national focus on improving resilience and response to managing chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) incidents (accidental, intentional or malicious intent). Until recently, there was limited practical guidance or advice on how to remediate contaminated environments (eg inhabited areas) and develop a recovery and remediation strategy, following a chemical, radiation or biological incident. The Centre for Radiation, Chemical and Environmental Hazards (CRCE) of Public Health England (PHE) has led on the development of the Chemical and Radiation Recovery Handbooks^{1,2} and it is committed to continue to maintain and update guidance and advice for recovery and remediation to ensure that it builds the evidence base for recovery strategies. This includes developing a Recovery Handbook for Biological Incidents, for which CRCE provides steer and support.

As part of this commitment, a Chemical and Radiation Recovery Navigation Tool (C&R RNT)³ is being developed in close collaboration with the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), the Food Standards Agency (FSA), Department for Transport (DfT) and the UK Government Decontamination Service (GDS)⁴. The purpose of the project is to develop an interactive support tool, to facilitate and guide recovery decision makers through the process of tailoring a recovery strategy when responding to any given chemical or radiation incident.

A pilot version of the C&R RNT for chemical incidents (inhabited areas, food production systems and water environments) is now available for testing on the legacy Health Protection Agency website, and can be accessed at <http://www.hpa.org.uk/ProductsServices/ChemicalsPoisons/RemediationAndEnvironmentalDecontamination/chemChemicalrecoverydecisionsupporttoolproject/> and at http://legacyassets.phe.org.uk/tools/CRT_elearning/index.html.

The project team will be working closely with scientists across CRCE, local authorities and other stakeholders to refine the C&R RNT during the course of the project and would like to invite readers to review the developing tool.

The developing tool also includes a recovery record form, as a method of capturing information on the handover from the acute response phase to the recovery phase, and assisting with recording decisions made during the evaluation of a recovery strategy (ie why recovery options were selected, based on the scientific evidence base and any constraints associated with them).

What's next

A final version of the Chemical RNT and recovery record forms will be published on PHE's recovery web pages in the next few weeks. Other recovery resources developed by the project team such as posters and articles will also be uploaded on to provide the user with a global vision in the use of these recovery tools.

Phase three of the project will begin in September 2014, and consist of the extension of the developing Chemical RNT to incorporate the new version of the Radiation Handbook that will be published by the beginning of autumn 2014 as an interim version. The expected completion date of the C&R RNT is June 2015.

Other aspects of the project include an evaluation of the evidence base for recovery options recommended in the UK Recovery Handbook for Radiation Incidents, which is expected to be updated and published in autumn 2014, and the development of an e-Learning module.

If you are interested or would like collaborate with us on the project then please contact the project team at chemical.recovery@phe.gov.uk.

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